

Frequency recognition in SSVEP-based BCI using Gaussian elimination-based canonical correlation analysis method

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Abstract

In this paper, a method is proposed to enhance the efficiency of frequency recognition by combining gaussian elimination and canonical correlation analysis methods. Gaussian elimination method uses backslash operation to calculate the correlation coefficients. Also, it uses to solve linear equations to calculate eigenvalues that reduce the CCA method's processing time. The method is evaluated using Information Transfer Rate (ITR) and CPU process time. We have used eight channels ($C = 8$) of P7, P3, Pz, P4, P8, O1, Oz and O2 data set of SSVEP signal for analyzing ITR using proposed GECCA method. The GECCA method shows the ITR of 8.62 bpm (bit per minute) for channel C. Furthermore, we have merged proposed GECCA with the existing multiset canonical correlation analysis method (MsetCCA) (MsetGECCA). The MsetGECCA shows the maximum ITR of 18.06 bpm for channel $C = 6$: P7, P3, P4, P8, O1 and O2 which is higher compared to the MsetCCA method's ITR value of $C = 6 = 13.11$ bpm. The promising results indicate that the proposed method can be suitable candidate for frequency recognition in SSVEP-based BCIs with more efficiency.

Keywords: Brain computer interface (BCI), Canonical correlation analysis (CCA), Gaussian elimination method.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the last few decades, the brain computer interface (BCI) is getting attention from the researchers due to the wide range of application including in signal processing, machine learning, neuroscience, abnormal brain structure detection, diagnosis and clinical rehabilitation [1-5]. The BCI system captures the brain signals and transfers to the electronic system (computer, smart devices) to perform the intended task. BCI signals can develop from various responses such as event-related potentials (as P300), event-related (de) synchronization (ERD/ERS), Steady-State Visually Evoked Potentials (SSVEPs) [6-8]. However, SSVEP based BCI is used more for higher information transfer rate (ITR), easy system configuration, and less user training. The SSVEP is the signal, generated from the occipital cortex by visual stimulations at specific frequencies [9, 10]. The frequencies are usually higher than 6Hz when a visual stimulus excites the retina [11]. The brain generates electrical wave with the same frequency of the stimulus as well as its harmonics. The SSVEP can be observed by electrodes from the surface of the scalp over the occipital and parietal lobes when the subject looks at a flickering light source with a constant frequency [12, 13]. Accordingly, the SSVEP-based BCI is designed to detect the desired commands by recognizing the SSVEP frequency in EEG. Although, original responses of SSVEP shows relatively static spectrums over time, they can defect a little bit due to the other EEG activities and surrounding noises [14].

To date, various methods have been proposed to recognize SSVEP. Lin *et al.* introduced first time the canonical correlation analysis (CCA)-based recognition method which is highly sensitive in frequency detection [11]. The CCA

method develop the maximum correlation between the EEG signals and the pre-constructed reference signals. But the main drawback of this method is background EEG signals. In another study, a Multiway CCA (MwayCCA) method is proposed to define the stimulus frequency for SSVEP-based BCI [15]. This method was implemented for generating significant reference signals from the sine-cosine signals and EEG tensor data which is used in correlation analysis for SSVEP recognition. Then multiple linear regression is applied to find the correlation between the optimized reference signals and test EEG data for SSVEP recognition. Though, the reference signal optimization is not followed based on the training data, still MwayCCA method use the pre-constructed signal. Also, this process is much more complex and requires more processing time than others. Nakanishi *et al.* proposed a method to integrate the unwanted frequency components to improve the frequency recognition of SSVEPs [16]. In this way, the interference frequencies could therefore provide further information to perceive the SSVEP frequency. Besides, a phase constrained CCA method (PCCA) is reported for SSVEP frequency recognition [17]. This method is used to achieve high accuracy by generating the phase information from the training data which is added to the reference signals. Another study introduces a multiset canonical correlation analysis (MsetCCA) method which is used to optimizing the reference signal for recognition of the SSVEP frequency [17]. The MsetCCA is developed to find maximum canonical variates from multiple sets of random variables. Though, the MsetCCA provides better performance than CCA and MwayCCA, it increases complexity and computational cost as well. Therefore, the development of an effective algorithm to recognize the SSVEP frequency with high accuracy and a short time window length (TW) will be considered crucial for the development of SSVEP-based BCI.

In this work, we have introduced gaussian elimination and canonical correlation analysis (GECCA) method to reduce the complexity of standard CCA method. In CCA, inverse matrix is used for the computation of eigenvalues which increases the computational complexity. Besides, left matrix division is applied in the proposed GECCA method for better estimation of the matrix inversion. Also, it enhances the calculation efficiency of eigenvalues resulting increases the ITR of SSVEP frequency recognition. In addition, CCA fails when the input matrix is not square which makes CCA activities incompatible in every circumstance. These issues can also be solved by the proposed GECCA method.

II. METHODS

A. SSVEP recognition Using CCA

The CCA-based detection technique relies on the reality that the brain signals can trace back a regular pattern with the similar frequency as like the stimulus frequency. In this technique, a linier combination is investigated for two data sets which is known as canonical variables. It also maximizes the correlation between canonical variables. CCA finds w_x and w_y from the sets of variables X and Y by the following question [18, 19].

$$\max_{w_x w_y} \rho = \frac{w_x^T C_{xy} w_y}{\sqrt{w_x^T C_{xx} w_x w_y^T C_{yy} w_y}} \quad (1)$$

where ρ denotes the canonical correlation, C_{xx} and C_{yy} refers covariance matrices within-sets, and C_{xy} indicates the between-sets of covariance matrix. The maximum canonical correlation (ρ) is obtained with respect to w_x and w_y . In

addition, X indicates the set of multi-channel EEG signal and Y is the set of reference signals for SSVEP based frequency recognition. The reference signals frequency with the maximum coefficient leads the stimulus of SSVEPs.

Figure 1: CCA Recognition procedure.

B. SSVEP recognition Using MsetCCA

For the lack of actual information in pre-constructed sine-cosine reference signal does not provide optimal of SSVEP frequency recognition. Recently, Zhang *et al.* has been proposed a new method (multiset canonical correlation analysis (MsetCCA)) for optimizing the reference signal [19]. In this method, the optimization processes of reference signal were done by extracting the similar attributes following the joint spatial filtering several times. The MsetCCA is an extended version of the CCA method which finds maximum correlation among canonical variates from multiple sets of variables. Here, various sets of random variables in $X_i \in R^{I \times J}$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, N$) which are standardized to have zero mean and unit variance. The objective function of MAXVAR is described as maximizing the general correlation between canonical variations [20].

$$\max_{w_1, \dots, w_N} \rho = \sum_{i \neq j} w_i^T X_i X_j^T w_j \quad (2)$$

The maximization from the Eq. 2 can be modified into the generalized eigenvalue problem,

$$(R - S)w = \rho Sw \quad (3)$$

where,

$$R = \begin{bmatrix} X_1 X_1^T & \dots & X_1 X_N^T \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ X_N X_1^T & \dots & X_N X_N^T \end{bmatrix}$$

$$S = \begin{bmatrix} X_1 X_1^T & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & \dots & X_N X_N^T \end{bmatrix}$$

$$w = \begin{bmatrix} w_1 \\ \vdots \\ w_N \end{bmatrix}$$

here linear transforms w_1, w_2, \dots, w_N which are the maximization of the canonical correlation from the multiple canonical variates $\tilde{Z}_i = w_i^T X_i$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, N$). The MsetCCA is introduced to obtain the multiple linear transforms $w_{1,m}, w_{2,m}, \dots, w_{N,m}$. These acquired canonical variations represent the common characteristics which are shared between several training data sets. These characteristics are presumed to indicate the accurate SSVEP features more correctly than the synthetic sine-cosine waves do. Following the calibration mentioned above procedure of optimization of reference signals, the maximum correlation coefficient ρ_m between test data set X and every optimum reference signal sets Y is evaluated by CCA.

C. Gaussian elimination

Gaussian elimination is an approach to solve the matrix equation of the following form [21],

$$A x = B \tag{4}$$

To accomplish the Gaussian elimination, it starts with the following equation,

$$\begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & \cdots & a_{1k} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & \cdots & a_{2k} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{k1} & a_{k2} & \cdots & a_{kk} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ \vdots \\ x_k \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} b_1 \\ b_2 \\ \vdots \\ b_k \end{bmatrix}$$

Therefore, compose the augmented matrix equation,

$$\begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & \cdots & a_{1k} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & \cdots & a_{2k} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{k1} & a_{k2} & \cdots & a_{kk} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} b_1 \\ b_2 \\ \vdots \\ b_k \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ \vdots \\ x_k \end{bmatrix}$$

Here, the matrix rows are labeled by column vector in the variables x . Now accomplish preparatory row operations to set the augmented matrix into an upper triangular form,

$$\begin{bmatrix} a'_{11} & a'_{12} & \cdots & a'_{1k} \\ 0 & a'_{22} & \cdots & a'_{2k} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \cdots & a'_{kk} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} b'_1 \\ b'_2 \\ \vdots \\ b'_k \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ \vdots \\ x_k \end{bmatrix}$$

Now, solving the equation of the k^{th} row for x_k , after that substitute back into the equation of the $(k-1)^{\text{st}}$ row to gain a solution for x_{k-1} , etc., following the formula,

$$x_i = \frac{1}{a'_{ii}} (b'_i - \sum_{j=i+1}^k a'_{ij} x_j) \tag{5}$$

A quick and effective modified CCA algorithm is suggested in this study that utilizes the operator of the backslash or left matrix division to solve the linear values of Eq. 5. This operator of the backslash is quick and effective than the reverse operator. The remaining algorithm is similar to the CCA strategy. Let us define the equation as,

$$G = \rho^2 = inv(C_{xx}) * C_{xy} * inv(C_{yy}) * C_{yx} \quad (6)$$

$$G = \rho^2 = A * B \quad (7)$$

where,

$$A = inv(C_{xx}) * C_{xy} = C_{xx}^{-1} C_{xy} \quad (8)$$

$$B = inv(C_{yy}) * C_{yx} = C_{yy}^{-1} C_{yx} \quad (9)$$

The parameters A and B from Eq. 6 and 7 are described as,

$$\left. \begin{aligned} A * C_{xx} &= C_{xy} \\ B * C_{yy} &= C_{yx} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (10)$$

Standard CCA approach performs matrix inverse operation to gain the value of A and B. In this work, we have used left matrix division. The comparable solution for matrix B can be described. The solution of Eqn. 6 and 7 can be written as,

$$\left. \begin{aligned} A &= C_{xx} \setminus C_{xy} \\ B &= C_{yy} \setminus C_{yx} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (11)$$

This will also simplify the equation and, therefore, the calculation time. To demonstrate that the operator of the left division is multiplied by the numerator and the denominator as,

$$\left. \begin{aligned} A &= C_{xx}^T * C_{xx} \setminus C_{xx}^T * C_{xy} \\ B &= C_{yy}^T * C_{yy} \setminus C_{yy}^T * C_{yx} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (12)$$

Using Gaussian elimination concept,

$$\left. \begin{aligned} A &= C_{xx}^T * (C_{xx} * C_{xx}^T) \setminus C_{xy} \\ B &= C_{yy}^T * (C_{yy} * C_{yy}^T) \setminus C_{yx} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (13)$$

Since $C_{xx}^T * C_{xx} = C_{yy}^T * C_{yy} = 1$, Eq. 13 can be written as,

$$\left. \begin{aligned} A &= C_{xx}^T \setminus C_{xy} \\ B &= C_{yy}^T \setminus C_{yx} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (14)$$

For a symmetric and square matrix $C_{xx}^T = C_{xx}$ and $C_{yy}^T = C_{yy}$. Thus Eq. 14 can be simplified as,

$$\left. \begin{aligned} A &= C_{xx} \setminus C_{xy} \\ B &= C_{yy} \setminus C_{yx} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (15)$$

Replacing A and B from Eq. 15 to Eq. 7

$$G = (C_{xx} \setminus C_{xy}) * (C_{yy} \setminus C_{yx}) \quad (16)$$

Without the inverse procedure, the value of G is acquired by merely introducing the left division operator, which increases efficiency and reduces the computational cost.

III. EXPERIMENTAL EVOLUTION

In this study, we have used epileptic data set (SSVEPdata.mat) which has 30 channels, and the sampling frequency is 250 Hz. Dataset contains four frequencies 6 Hz, 8 Hz, 9 Hz, and 10 Hz with the duration of 4s each [22, 23]. The reference signal is optimized by running the training data 19 times and left-out method is considered for validation [23]. This operation is repeated twenty times to validate each run performs once. The average precision of recognition is assessed on the immediate validation of 20 runs for the CCA technique [24]. A very significant index for evaluating a BCI scheme is the rate of information transfer (ITR). ITR is displayed in bits per minute by the transmitted data [25].

$$ITR = \frac{60}{N} [\log_2 N + p \log_2 N + (1 - p) \log_2 \frac{(1-p)}{N-1}] \quad (17)$$

where N defines the signal length, and p indicates the probability of accuracy. Furthermore, the proposed method also shows the estimated computational time to check the feasibility in BCIs. The computational time defines the time consume in preprocessing, CCA-based feature extraction, and classification.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Results

EEG signals are collected from healthy subjects and employed to show the performance comparison of GECCA method to the existing CCA, the MsetCCA methods. Also, we show the performance of MsetGECCA (merged GECCA with MsetCCA method). For the CCA methods, first we have investigated the effects of varying harmonics H on the accuracy of frequency recognition where number of H is predefined. Figure 2 shows the average accuracy of SSVEP recognition, which is acquired by CCA, GECCA, and MsetCCA with the H of 1 to 3 at different time window lengths (TWs), respectively. Though, the predefined harmonic H is not required for the MsetCCA method, provide the same accuracy for $H = 1, 2,$ and 3 (see Table 1). The CCA exhibits a higher accuracy when H is 2 and 3 than 1. Therefore, we have used $H = 2$ as a fixed harmonic for channel selection.

Figure 2. Average frequency recognition accuracies obtained by CCA, GECCA, MsetCCA and MsetGECCA respectively for harmonic (a) $H=1$, (b) $H=2$, and (c) $H=3$.

TABLE I
Process time for CCA, GECCA, MsetCCA, MsetGECCA for harmonics H=1, 2 and 3.

Methods	Process Time (s),	Process Time (s),	Process Time(s),
	H=1	H=2	H=3
CCA	1.06	1.02	0.91
GECCA	1.01	0.94	0.79
MsetCCA	11.30	11.92	10.99
MsetGECCA	10.90	11.48	10.57

According to Table I, it seems that CCA and GECCA have the same accuracy, but the process time of CCA is higher than GECCA. Process time for the MsetCCA and MsetGECCA is much higher than the CCA and GECCA. But MsetGECCA takes less time than MsetCCA. In terms of ITR, MsetCCA has the higher value compared to all other methods for all H = 1, 2 and 3. Table II shows the ITR for all methods. The CCA has the lowest ITR compared to others method. The ITR of GECCA is much higher than the general CCA method (see Table II).

TABLE II
Information Transfer Rate (ITR) for CCA, GECCA, MsetCCA, MsetGECCA for harmonics H = 1, 2 and 3.

Method	ITR (bpm)	ITR (bpm)	ITR (bpm)
	H=1	H=2	H=3
CCA	2.28	3.73	4.40
GECCA	8.14	15.09	15.09
MsetCCA	15.80	18.06	18.06
MsetGECCA	14.41	17.28	16.53

With set H = 2, the further study is for investigating the impacts of varying the amount of channels C on the precision of frequency recognition. Figure 3 shows the accuracies for various methods with the channels C = 4, 6, and 8. The accuracies are lowest at C = 4 and highest at C = 6. The MsetCCA and MsetGECCA show higher accuracy than CCA for all C = 4, 6, 8.

Figure 3: Accuracies of average SSVEP in the CCA, GECCA, MsetCCA and MsetGECCA methods, respectively for (a) C = 4, (b) C = 6, and (c) C=8 when time window lengths are from 1s to 4s.

Figure 4 shows the process time for the CCA, GECCA, MsetCCA and MsetGECCA methods, respectively, for the channels C = 4, 6 and 8. Though, MsetCCA and MsetGECCA provide higher accuracy (see Figure 3), the processing time of MsetCCA are much higher than MsetGECCA as well as GECCA. So, it may not be a proper way to use

MsetCCA in real-time devices. Again, GECCA provides less processing time; we can replace CCA with GECCA (see Figure 4).

Figure 4: Process time for CCA, GECCA, MsetCCA and MsetGECCA for channels C = 4, 6 and 8.

In addition, ITR is another performance indicator of BCI. ITR of CCA is very low at the C = 4, 6 and 8 (see Figure 5). In general, ITR of MsetCCA was the highest. But, the MsetGECCA shows the highest ITR among all other methods when channels are set C= 4, 6 and 8. Among the all channels (C=4, 6 and 8), channel C=6 shows the highest ITR which is 18.06.

Figure 5: Information Transfer Rate (ITR) is of the CCA, GECCA, MsetCCA and MsetGECCA, respectively for channels C = 4, 6 and 8.

B. Discussion

An offline analysis has been demonstrated in this work. The coefficient range for the standard CCA, GECCA, MsetCCA, and MsetGECCA was from 0 to 1 due to calculate the canonical correlation between the test data and the reference signals. Here, largest coefficient of CCA is used because of it conveys the most information and true under ideal conditions. However, noise is a reason to contaminate of the real EEG signals. Also, discontinuous phase transitions can be happened to the real EEG signals. These two factors help to spread the information across more

than one coefficient and reasonable to exploit additional coefficients. Moreover, multiple channels were used to minimizing the noise and discontinuous phase transitions to enhance the result associated with the CCA approach.

To obtain the demixing matrix, the CCA algorithm mainly depends on the inverse operation. The CCA algorithm will fail when the input matrix is not square. The left division operator-based GECCA algorithm offers a solution either input matrix is square or not. However, the inverse procedure is time-consuming and computationally complicated. The suggested GECCA algorithm is quicker than CCA to obtain the separation of the source based on correlation by using the operator of the left division instead of reverse operation. The GECCA algorithms use the left matrix division operator quicker than the inverse matrix technique used in the CCA algorithm. The suggested technique of GECCA is, therefore, quicker than the CCA. In addition, the division of the left matrix enables better estimates of the inversion matrix. The speed of execution or computation is assessed by the time elapsed and ITR. The MsetGECCA provides highest ITR for the harmonics $H = 1, 2, 3$ compared to other methods. Finally, we can anticipate that the proposed GECCA method will be effective to make decision of SSVEP frequency recognition.

III. CONCLUSION

In the summary, a method (GECCA) is proposed by combining Gaussian Elimination method with the Canonical Correlation Analysis method to reduce computational complexity as well as frequency recognition accuracy. We have used 30 channels based SSVEPdata.mat data set for computational analysis. The proposed GECCA method shows the lowest processing time of 0.79 s while $H=3$ and maximum ITR of 15.09 bpm. Also, we have introduced another method (MsetGECCA) which shows the maximum ITR of 18.06 bpm and 11.88 bpm for the channels $C=6$ and $C=8$, respectively. Furthermore, we can anticipate that the proposed methods perform better than the existing methods in term of ITR and process time which can lead to frequency recognition with high accuracy in the real time applications.

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REFERENCES

1. Friman, O., I. Volosyak, and A. Graser, *Multiple channel detection of steady-state visual evoked potentials for brain-computer interfaces*. IEEE transactions on biomedical engineering, 2007. **54**(4): p. 742-750.
2. Hekmatmanesh, A., et al., *A combination of CSP-based method with soft margin SVM classifier and generalized RBF kernel for imagery-based brain computer interface applications*. Multimedia Tools and Applications, 2020: p. 1-29.
3. Cha, H.-S., C.-H. Han, and C.-H. Im, *Prediction of Individual User's Dynamic Ranges of EEG Features from Resting-State EEG Data for Evaluating Their Suitability for Passive Brain-Computer Interface Applications*. Sensors, 2020. **20**(4): p. 988.
4. Abiri, R., et al., *A comprehensive review of EEG-based brain-computer interface paradigms*. Journal of neural engineering, 2019. **16**(1): p. 011001.
5. Kumar, G.K. and M.R. Reddy, *Latent common source extraction via a generalized canonical correlation framework for frequency recognition in SSVEP based brain-computer interfaces*. Journal of neural engineering, 2019. **16**(4): p. 046004.
6. Alkawadri, R., *Brain-Computer Interface (BCI) Applications in Mapping of Epileptic Brain Networks Based on Intracranial-EEG: An Update*. Frontiers in Neuroscience, 2019. **13**: p. 191.
7. Park, S., et al. *Development of an Online Home Appliance Control System Using Augmented Reality and an SSVEP-Based Brain-Computer Interface*. in *2020 8th International Winter Conference on Brain-Computer Interface (BCI)*. 2020. IEEE.
8. Kumar, G.K. and M.R. Reddy, *Constructing an exactly periodic subspace for enhancing SSVEP based BCI*. Advanced Engineering Informatics, 2020. **44**: p. 101046.

9. Zhou, C., et al., *D-Shaped Photonic Crystal Fiber Plasmon Sensors Based on Self-Reference Channel*. IEEE Photonics Technology Letters, 2020. **32**(10): p. 589-591.
10. Ravindran, K.K.G. and R.R. Machireddy. *Exactly Periodic Spatial Filter for SSVEP Based BCIs*. in *2018 International Conference on Cyberworlds (CW)*. 2018. IEEE.
11. Lin, Z., et al., *Frequency recognition based on canonical correlation analysis for SSVEP-based BCIs*. IEEE transactions on biomedical engineering, 2006. **53**(12): p. 2610-2614.
12. Jiang, J., et al., *Incorporation of dynamic stopping strategy into the high-speed SSVEP-based BCIs*. Journal of neural engineering, 2018. **15**(4): p. 046025.
13. Shi, M., et al. *A method for SSVEP recognition based on weighted canonical correlation analysis*. in *2019 IEEE Symposium Series on Computational Intelligence (SSCI)*. 2019. IEEE.
14. Liu, Q., et al., *recent development of signal processing algorithms for SSVEP-based brain computer interfaces*. J. Med. Biol. Eng., 2014. **34**(4): p. 299-309.
15. Zhang, Y., et al., *L1-regularized multiway canonical correlation analysis for SSVEP-based BCI*. IEEE transactions on neural systems and rehabilitation engineering, 2013. **21**(6): p. 887-896.
16. Nakanishi, M., et al., *A comparison study of canonical correlation analysis based methods for detecting steady-state visual evoked potentials*. PloS one, 2015. **10**(10): p. e0140703.
17. Zhang, Y., et al., *Frequency recognition in SSVEP-based BCI using multiset canonical correlation analysis*. International journal of neural systems, 2014. **24**(04): p. 1450013.
18. Hakvoort, G., B. Reuderink, and M. Obbink, *Comparison of PSDA and CCA detection methods in a SSVEP-based BCI-system*. Centre for Telematics & Information Technology University of Twente, 2011.
19. Liu, T., et al., *Fusing canonical coefficients for frequency recognition in SSVEP-based BCI*. IEEE Access, 2019. **7**: p. 52467-52472.
20. Jiao, Y., et al., *A novel multilayer correlation maximization model for improving CCA-based frequency recognition in SSVEP brain-computer interface*. International journal of neural systems, 2018. **28**(04): p. 1750039.
21. Roy, V., et al., *Gaussian elimination-based novel canonical correlation analysis method for EEG motion artifact removal*. Journal of Healthcare Engineering, 2017. **2017**.
22. Li, Z., et al., *Spatial fusion of maximum signal fraction analysis for frequency recognition in SSVEP-based BCI*. Biomedical Signal Processing and Control, 2020. **61**: p. 102042.
23. Wang, Y., et al., *A benchmark dataset for SSVEP-based brain-computer interfaces*. IEEE Transactions on Neural Systems and Rehabilitation Engineering, 2016. **25**(10): p. 1746-1752.
24. Yang, C., et al., *A dynamic window recognition algorithm for SSVEP-based brain-computer interfaces using a spatio-temporal equalizer*. International journal of neural systems, 2018. **28**(10): p. 1850028.
25. Zhang, Y., et al., *Correlated component analysis for enhancing the performance of SSVEP-based brain-computer interface*. IEEE Transactions on Neural Systems and Rehabilitation Engineering, 2018. **26**(5): p. 948-956.